

The Horizon 2020 project GEOFIT entered the second part of its development and started the demonstration activities!

Involving 24 partners from 10 European countries, GEOFIT is dedicated to developing innovative enhanced geothermal systems, specifically designed for geothermal based retrofitting. The GEOFIT partnership considers that the implementation of a global, effective, energy-efficient retrofitting strategy for the stock of existing buildings in Europe, will boost the adoption of appropriate geothermal based energy-efficient building retrofitting technologies and methods. Our holistic approach uses the most innovative methods and tools and is being demonstrated in different climate and soil conditions across Europe.

As we kick-off 2021, let's see what we have been up to!

This past year has been intense! One side of our activities has been led by the completion of the innovative geothermal systems designs that will be implemented at each demo site to demonstrate that our easy-to-install solution is capable of providing efficient heating and cooling. Our partners have been hard at work and you can already read some of these results in our publications section below!

The other side of our activities has been pilot oriented, as we started the installation works in the demo site in Spain and have greatly advanced preparing the terrain for the installations at our demo site in Italy. In the meantime, our French and Irish demo sites are working hard to have everything ready to start the works in early 2021. Make sure to take a closer look at the highlights below to learn more of these activities!

PROJECT NEWS

GEOFIT JOINT H2020 WORKSHOP AT SUSTAINABLE PLACES 2020

On October 29th, a virtual workshop organized by RHC with fellow H2020 sister projects took place within SP2020. Titled "Renewable Heating and Cooling Solutions for Buildings and Industry", the workshop organised a series of round tables focusing on 4 different topics.

[▶ LEARN MORE](#)

GET TO KNOW OUR GEOBIM PLATFORM

A series of 10 videos explaining GEOBIM was launched in November! See our IDP experts explain how it can assess and verify the integration of the GEOFIT solutions in specific cases by developing its respective BIM models over a geographical information layer.

[▶ LEARN MORE](#)

A LOOK AT STAKEHOLDERS AND MARKETS

Curious about the market uptake of Geothermal technologies? In this article by R2M, we take a closer look at the wide spectrum of shallow geothermal energy stakeholders in order to develop commercial-ready solutions.

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DEMO SITES

GROUND PENETRATING RADAR ANALYSIS AT PERUGIA

On October 2020, IDS GeoRadar was at the GEOFIT pilot in Perugia to perform a Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) survey over the area where excavation works are going to be executed.

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GEOTHERMAL CATCHMENT FIELD COMPLETED AT THE SANT CUGAT

During August, works started at the Sant Cugat demo-site started! The geothermal catchment field, performed by CDP, was completed as well as the horizontal connection between the wells and the plant room where the ground-source heat pump will be installed.

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STRUCTURAL MONITORING AT SANT CUGAT PILOT

Partners SIART and IDS GEORADAR were at the Sant Cugat pilot with a Hydra-G system to monitor real-time measurements of sub-millimetric displacements in the administrative building and in the primary school. Also several accelerometers were installed to monitor vibrations.

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PUBLICATIONS & CONFERENCES

Design requirements for condensation-free operation of high-temperature cooling systems in Mediterranean climate

Paper. Partners: KTH / UPONOR

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A novel ROM methodology to support the estimation of the energy savings under the Measurement and Verification protocol

Conference Paper presented at IBIPSA UK. Partner: NUIG Galway

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An integrated HBIM simulation approach for energy retrofit of historical buildings implemented in a case study of a medieval fortress in Italy

Paper. Partner: UNIPG

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Data collected by coupling fix and renewable sensors for addressing urban microclimate variability in historical Italian city

Paper. Partner: UNIPG

[▶ DOWNLOAD & READ](#)

Environmental sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Historical Buildings: GeoFit Project Implementation in the Case Study of a medieval fortress in Perugia

Conference Paper presented at IBIPSA Rome. Partner: UNIPG

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Erdwärmepumpen für die energieeffiziente Gebäudesanierung

Conference Paper presented at DKV. Partner: AIT

[▶ DOWNLOAD & READ](#)

Geothermal Power: Monitoring the Building Response During Installation

Conference Paper presented at IWSHM. Partner: IDS GEORADAR

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MEET OUR PARTNERS !

If you are new to our project, this is the place to start!

Watch these short interviews and hear in their own words who they are and their role within GEOFIT!

KTH & UPONOR

KTH Royal Institute of Technology has become one of Europe's leading technical and engineering universities, as well as a key center of intellectual talent and innovation. Uponor is a leading international supplier of plumbing, heating, and cooling systems for the residential and commercial building markets.

[▶ WATCH NOW](#)

OSCHNER

Ochsner Wärmepumpen was founded in 1978 as one of the first companies in Europe producing heat pumps on an industrial scale, being a well-known producer of innovative heat pump systems covering all types of heat sources and capacities ranging from 2 to 1.600 kW.

[▶ WATCH NOW](#)

GROENHOLLAND

Groenholland Geo-energy systems is a company providing consulting services with regard to the design of shallow geothermal energy systems, site characterization, and building systems simulations. Groenholland furthermore develops, builds, installs, and maintains turn-key ground source energy systems.

[▶ WATCH NOW](#)

FAHRENHEIT

Founded in 2002, as a spin-off company of Fraunhofer Institute of Solar Energy Systems (ISE), it is the pioneering company in small capacity adsorption chillers, holding 22 national and international patent families on thermal refrigeration and technological solutions utilizing solid sorbents like silica gel and zeolite.

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IDP

IDP Ingeniería y Arquitectura Iberia S.L.U. is an innovative and multidisciplinary SME with services ranging from civil & infrastructure engineering, environmental sciences, ICT to project management & consultancy.

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IDDS WEBINAR

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- [YouTube.com](https://www.youtube.com)

Consortium partners

Coordinator: R2M

